

**OUR 5TH NEWSLETTER
IS HERE!**

Dear friends, partners and colleagues,

It has been a few very busy months for e-SAFE partners, with the local pilot activities now in full swing! In Timișoara, e-SAFE partners worked closely with the students and teachers of Liceul Sportiv Banatul to deliver a detailed renovation project through a co-design process. Ending on a high note, the renovation plan was unveiled during a public event at Politehnica University of Timișoara, with a special feature on Romanian TV.

In this newsletter we are explaining how the renovation plan for the Timișoara pilot has been elaborated thanks to a unique participatory approach, with students and teachers involved at every step of the journey. Through several interviews, we are sharing the voices of the people involved in this exciting process, such as the school principal, the municipal representative, the students and project partners.

We are now preparing the co-design activities for the Bucharest pilot, which will kick off in the next weeks, so stay tuned for this!

I hope this newsletter will be full of ideas and that it will inspire many when it comes to implementing seismic and energy-efficient solutions for renovation, crucial for the future of our buildings.

Happy reading!

Sunny regards from Catania,

Giuseppe Margani & the e-SAFE team

What does it mean to co-design a renovation plan?

CO-DESIGN

What are the benefits?

- Access to users' knowledge and experience
- Achieve greater acceptance of the design choices
- Raise awareness on the importance of achieving energy efficient and seismic proof buildings

- Share their needs and knowledge on how to use the building
- Opportunity to express their creativity
- Take part in a collaborative process and make decisions on common spaces and building maintenance

The word "**co-design**" refers to a participatory, co-creative, and open design approach where building's end-users directly collaborate through the entire design process with design experts so that they can identify together the best design solutions within a common framework.

Zoom on the e-SAFE pilot in Timișoara: Liceul Sportiv Banatul

Since last December, Liceul Sportiv Banatul students and teachers, together with the Politehnica University of Timișoara, met weekly with the e-SAFE consortium, in order to co-design an actionable renovation plan for their school through a participatory process.

The co-design process in Timisoara

778

Students learned extensively about the health, safety, and environmental benefits of building renovation, and collectively created a stepwise renovation plan, prioritizing deep energy renovations, as well as structural earthquake safety renovations that would safeguard the school from potential seismic threats. The plan introduces significant energy and financial savings.

From cardboard model...

After the co-design process, what does the renovation plan look like?

...to digital representation of the renovation plan:

Building on the discussion with the students, e-SAFE partners were able to finalise the renovation plan, taking into account their needs and ideas. The final plan also integrates one of e-SAFE's key technologies, e-EXOS, which consists in strengthening the existing structure with a metal exoskeleton. Students also had the opportunity to share ideas on how to improve the outdoor area around the building, by adding comfortable benches to relax and read in between classes.

Green and seismic safe school for Timișoara

The last e-SAFE project meeting, taking place in Timișoara on 29th-30th March, ended on a high note, with partners, school representatives and students unveiling the final renovation plan in front of the public. The event, organized by e-SAFE partners BPIE and UNICT in collaboration with the Timișoara Local Platform, and hosted by the POLITEHNICA University of Timișoara, was an excellent opportunity to learn, discuss and imagine how to achieve greener and safer schools for all.

Representatives from Liceul Banatul, POLITEHNICA University of Timișoara, and e-SAFE project gathered all together for a constructive and stimulating discussion. The public actively discussed the many benefits of such a renovation, and addressed the next steps of the project, highlighting the need for adequate funding to make it come to life.

[Read the full news here!](#)

e-SAFE buildings on TV!

e-SAFE partner's **Laura Saija** from UNICT, together with **Ramona Roman**, the Director of the pilot school, was invited on the local TV to talk about e-SAFE, the crucial role of Liceul Sportiv Banatul, as well as the importance of securing funding for the project.

Laura Saija reminded that it is crucial to demonstrate to the students that their ideas and creativity matter and to set an example for other schools and municipalities in terms of renovation and codesign that involves children and encourages future generations to think about renovation and sustainability.

Watch the full interview
on YouTube!

The faces behind the project: Interview with Dr. Ioan Silviu Dobosi

Dr. Dobosi is associate professor of architecture at the Polytechnic University of Timișoara and president of the Romanian Association of Building Services Engineers.

What has been the highlight of the whole experience for you?

«I found **the co-design approach itself to be highly innovative. The end result is a renovation plan that fits users' needs much better than if the architect or engineer just comes in with a ready-made solution, and the people involved learn something and take ownership of the renovation in a way they wouldn't otherwise. It's a completely different experience for everyone involved.** Students of the school received knowledge related to comfort, building structure, energy management, and even the aesthetic aspects. And they care more about energy savings than they did before. In this case, I think it was really valorising for the children involved, to be heard, to have their ideas considered and, in some cases, taken up in the final renovation plans.»

Our youth deserve to be educated in buildings which are safe, comfortable and suitable for the educational process. Renovation needs to happen much more, much faster.

Ioan Silviu DOBOSI
President of the Romanian Association
of Building
Services Engineers

Read the full interview
here!

The faces behind the project: Interview with Prof. Ramona Roman

Upon the completion of the co-design process in Liceul Sportiv Banatul in March 2023, we sat down with the school's director, Prof Ramona Roman, to discuss her experience with the process. Professor Roman was one of the biggest supporters of e-SAFE, she sold the project to the schoolboard, to teachers and students, and acted as the direct link between e-SAFE and the school throughout the process.

What was your motivation to work with e-SAFE?

« Because the school's buildings are very old, and in need of renovation. **Our energy bills are too high, and the buildings' inefficiency directly impacts students' comfort and performance. For example, classrooms are uncomfortably hot during the summer months, in June and July, when they're writing their exams. It's hard to concentrate and perform your best in a humid, overheated room.** We also pay too much for heating. Being a public school built in 1948, the school receives heat from the district heating system, which dates back to the communist regime. The system is controlled by the city, we can't turn the heating off when we don't need it. It gets too hot very often, and so we open the windows. It's inefficient, and it costs too much.»

Read the full interview
here!

e-SAFE in Timișoara: discover our playlist on YouTube!

5:26

Prof. Laura Saija interviewed at TVR

SUBSCRIBE

1:39

Ramona Roman tells us the impressions ...

SUBSCRIBE

1:17

Short interview to Carmen Proteasa

SUBSCRIBE

3:53

e-SAFE featured in TVR Timișoara

SUBSCRIBE

1:19

Ioan Silviu Dobosi talks about the key points...

SUBSCRIBE

 WATCH NOW

News from the Bucharest local platform

On April 18th, e-SAFE partners from the Universities of Catania and Bologna kicked off the preparations for the co-design process that will take place later this year in Bucharest.

Partners met with technicians and the director of AMCCRR (Administrația Municipală pentru Consolidarea Clădirilor cu Risc Seismic) to present the e-SAFE project and discuss the next step for co-designing a renovation plan for the multi-family apartment building.

Partners also met with the residents to present the project, and gather their insights and perceptions related to indoor environmental quality, seismic resistance, heating system, and energy bills.

Discover more

Future conferences e-SAFE will attend

The 35th AESOP Annual Congress 2023 - 11-15 July 2023

Every year, AESOP holds its Annual Congress, hosted by one of member universities. The 35th 2023 congress is held in Łódź and will focus on *Integrated Planning on a World of Turbulence*.

Building Simulation Conference, 4-6 September 2023

Following the successful BS2021 in Bruges, Shanghai will take the relay in hosting the next worldwide Building Simulation Conference! The regional affiliate, IBPSA-China, is honored to present an efficient, interactive, warm and safe reunion to the community that will invite the participants to an interactive discussion in hope for a better simulation in *low carbon design, operation and city development*.

The 18th SDEWES - 24-29 September 2023

The 18th Conference on Sustainable Development of Energy, Water and Environment Systems (SDEWES) is dedicated to the advancement and dissemination of knowledge on methods, policies and technologies for *increasing the sustainability of development by de-coupling growth from the use of natural resources and by a transition to a knowledge-based economy*. All taking into account the economic, environmental and social pillars of sustainable development.

18TH CONFERENCE ON
SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT
OF ENERGY, WATER AND
ENVIRONMENT SYSTEMS

SEPTEMBER 24-29 2023,
DUBROVNIK, CROATIA

e-SAFE stakeholder community

If you'd like to stay abreast on all news related to e-SAFE and seismic renovations in general, we invite you to join our *e-SAFE stakeholder community*.

Join the stakeholders community

Thanks for your attention!

Be sure to **follow us** on **Social Media** to keep upon all the latest **e-SAFE news!**

Partners

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 893135.

